

Original Article

Effect of Numbered Heads Together Strategy on Application Level of Achievement in Chemistry for 9th Grade Students

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Abstract

This research aimed to address the issue of rote memorization by exploring alternative teaching strategy to enhance student's application level of achievements and retention in chemistry. The study employed a quasi-experimental design, with the target population consisting of secondary level students in the Science Group, aged 14 to 17. A school was selected using purposive sampling with over 60 students of grade IX two sections was chosen to ensure an adequate sample size. One section was chosen as the experimental group and other as control group. The experimental group received instruction using the Numbered Heads Together cooperative learning strategy. While second section the control group was taught using traditional lecture-based strategy. The key components of NHT strategy are Heterogeneous Teams and Common team goals. Both groups were taught the same curriculum. Assessment was developed by the researcher and validated by pedagogy experts and chemistry experts, were used to measure student's achievements and retention for application, analysis and evaluation levels of Blooms taxonomy. The scoring rubric focused on indicators such as accurate explanation of content, Clarity and Organization. The collected data were analysed using mean scores from the pre-test, post-test and retention test in both groups. The independent sample t-test and paired sample t-test were used to compare the mean scores of the experimental and control group for application level of achievement and retention. The analysis of the data showed that NHT strategy has a significant effect on student's application level of achievements and retention. The findings of this study contribute to the understanding of the effect of the NHT strategy in improving student's achievements and retention for application level in chemistry and provide insights for educators and policy makers seeking innovative strategies to enhance student's achievements and retention for application level in chemistry.

Keywords: Achievement, Retention, Numbered Heads Together Strategy, Cooperative Learning

INTRODUCTION

The present study is grounded in a synthesis of constructivist, social, and cooperative learning theories, all of which emphasize the importance of active student engagement, collaboration, and cognitive processing especially at higher-order levels of Bloom's taxonomy, such as the application level. These theoretical underpinnings support the use of the Numbered Heads Together (NHT) strategy as an effective approach to enhance students' achievement and retention in chemistry. At its core, the constructivist learning theory posits that learners actively construct meaning based on experiences and social interactions. Vygotsky's (1978) social constructivist theory, particularly the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), highlights the importance of collaborative learning, where students learn more effectively with the support of peers and teachers than they would independently. In this context, the NHT strategy operationalizes ZPD by structuring peer interaction, allowing students to scaffold each other's

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understanding and bridge the gap between current knowledge and potential development. This collaborative dialogue supports deeper conceptual understanding and fosters the transfer of learning to novel situations, a critical component of application-level thinking in Bloom's taxonomy.

Aligned with this is cooperative learning theory, notably the frameworks developed by Kagan (2009) and Johnson & Johnson (1999). Kagan's PIES principles Positive Interdependence, Individual Accountability, Equal Participation, and Simultaneous Interaction are central to the implementation of NHT. These principles ensure that all group members actively participate, support one another, and are held accountable for their contributions. When applied to the learning of chemistry, these interactions promote the ability to apply learned scientific concepts to solve problems, reason through chemical phenomena, and engage in higher-order thinking processes. This sustained engagement enhances not only comprehension but also application and critical thinking. The application level, as defined in Bloom's Revised Taxonomy (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001), involves using learned material in new and meaningful contexts. This level is often underdeveloped in traditional teacher-centered classrooms that focus on rote memorization. By contrast, NHT cultivates a learning environment where students collaboratively analyze, discuss, and apply knowledge, thereby deepening understanding and promoting meaningful learning outcomes. The application level is particularly relevant in chemistry education, where students must use theoretical knowledge to solve practical problems, conduct experiments, or analyze reactions.

Additionally, the study considers the concept of achievement as "the information or skills acquired in the subjects taught in school, often ascertained by test results, teacher-assigned grades, or both" (Carter, 1959). This reflects short-term learning outcomes and is often closely tied to specific instructional objectives. On the other hand, retention is defined as "the ability to retain learned material or abilities in a way that enables efficient recall and application when required," reflecting long-term memory and learning durability (Ausubel, 2012). In this study, application-level achievement and retention are measured using assessments designed to evaluate students' ability to transfer and apply knowledge to unfamiliar chemical contexts both immediately and after a delay. The NHT strategy, as defined by Sari & Surya (2017), involves students working in groups to discuss and respond to questions collaboratively, promoting accountability, interaction, and positive interdependence. These features make NHT particularly well-suited for fostering application-level achievement and retention in chemistry, where understanding and using concepts in real-life or novel scientific scenarios is crucial. So this study integrates theories of social constructivism, cooperative learning, and cognitive taxonomy to establish a strong theoretical and conceptual basis. By combining peer collaboration (Vygotsky), structured interaction (Kagan), and cognitively challenging tasks (Bloom), the NHT strategy is posited to significantly improve students' application-level achievement and retention in secondary-level chemistry.

Conceptual Frame Work

This conceptual framework illustrates how the Numbered Heads Together (NHT) strategy enhances 9th-grade students' application-level achievement in chemistry. By engaging students in cooperative group discussions where each member is accountable, the NHT strategy promotes active participation and peer interaction. This collaborative learning environment fosters deeper understanding, enabling students to apply concepts effectively in new situations, thus improving their application-level achievement and retention as defined by Bloom's Taxonomy.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

The NHT-cooperative learning strategy enhances students' cognitive success both at the lowest and highest cognitive levels. The capacity to analyze, evaluate, apply and retain information is the cognitive skills that the students acquired using NHT-cooperative learning strategy (Leasa & Corebima, 2017) Hence, many studies have praised the virtues of the NHT strategy, but only a handful has examined the effect of strategy implementation on student's achievements and retention. So, this study seeks to complete previous research by using a cooperative learning strategy based on NHT in secondary school for chemistry learning. So poor retention and low

achievements of students in chemistry at secondary level is the problem. To resolve this problem, this study has checked the effect of NHT strategy on student's application level with respect to student retention and achievements in chemistry at secondary level.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the research study were to:

- Investigate the effect of NHT teaching strategy on application level of achievements in chemistry for secondary level students.
- Find the effect of NHT teaching strategy on application level of retention in chemistry for secondary level students.

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁: NHT strategy has no effect on achievements of application level of secondary school students in subject of chemistry.

H₀₂: NHT strategy has no effect on application level of retention in chemistry for secondary level students.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study was quantitative and quasi-experimental in nature, employing a pre-test post-test non-equivalent control group design, as random assignment of students was not feasible in school setting. The design was selected to test the cause-and-effect relationship between the independent variable Teaching Strategies and the dependent variable (application-level of achievement and retention in chemistry). The population comprised secondary-level science students. A convenient sample of 9th-grade science students from Government Girls High School (GGHS), Nagri Tutial, Tehsil Lora, was selected. One intact class was assigned as the experimental group and the other as the control group. The experimental group was taught using the Numbered Heads Together (NHT) strategy, while the control group received instruction through the lecture method. Pretest and posttest scores on an application-level chemistry achievement test were used to assess the impact of the intervention.

Research Design

The study was quasi experimental in nature. Pretest post-test non-equivalent control group design was used. This design was used because this design aids in testing the cause and effect relationship between the independent and dependent variables. In this design an individual's random assignment to treatment and control group is not practicable or acceptable in schools. So, the intact class was used as an experimental and control group without randomization. When a randomized controlled experiment is not practical, researchers may choose a non-equivalent control group design. Non-equivalent control group designs are widely used in observational studies, in which researchers watch and compare naturally occurring groups (Campbell & Stanley, 2015). Without disturbing the natural settings of classes one group is considered as control and other was taken as experimental group. The researcher compared the post-test and retention test results of the experimental group and control group. Therefore, by keeping the requirements of the study, an intact group pre-test and post-test design was used.

Intervention

The intervention was implemented over a period of six weeks in the experimental group using the Numbered Heads Together (NHT) strategy. Students were divided into small groups of 4–5 members and each member was assigned a number. During each chemistry lesson, the teacher posed application-level questions for achievement and retention related to the topic. Students were instructed to “put their heads together” to discuss and agree on the answer. After discussion, the teacher randomly called a number, and the student with that number from each group responded on behalf of their team. This process encouraged equal participation, accountability, and active engagement. Lessons were designed to target application-level objectives for achievement and retention based on Bloom's taxonomy. Meanwhile, the control group was taught the same content using the traditional lecture method without structured peer interaction.

Participants of the Study

This study involved female 9th-grade science students from Government Girls High School (GGHS) Nagri Tutial, Tehsil Lora, District Abbottabad. Out of 851 GGHS in the district, with approximately 5,418 students enrolled in 9th grade according to the 2024–2025 Annual School Census Report, the selected school met the inclusion criteria of having at least two science sections with a minimum of 30 students each. Using purposive

sampling, one section was assigned as the experimental group taught through the Numbered Heads Together (NHT) strategy, while the other served as the control group receiving traditional instruction.

Instruments

An achievement test developed by researchers was used as pretest, posttest and retention test for this experimental study. It was developed by following three major steps: designing the test, conducting a test trial, revising the test and further preparing the test. The data for this study was gathered through the administration of achievement test designed to assess student's application level of retention and achievements in chemistry, covered in Chapter 1 Fundamentals of Chemistry, Chapter 2 Structure of Atom and Chapter 3 Periodic Table and Periodicity of Properties of textbook board Peshawar. The test was designed with correspondence to Bloom's taxonomy level of application. The test contains 10 multiple choice questions of 10 marks and 6 short questions of 30 marks.

Procedure

At the beginning of the academic year two intact sections of science group class 9th were taken as sample from a Government Girls High School before the classes were scheduled. One section was randomly chosen as a treatment group and the other was a control group. First, the pretest was taken from both groups. The control group was taught through lecture method for 4 weeks. The content for teaching was Chapter 1 Fundamentals of Chemistry Chapter 2 Structure of Atom and Chapter 3 Periodic Table and Periodicity of Properties. The teacher followed all the steps of NHT cooperative learning strategy for teaching all three chapters to treatment group. After completion of all units' post-test was taken from both groups. After a gap of four weeks after the posttest, a retention test was taken for all units. Data was collected personally from test results of class 9th students in chemistry before and after intervention of treatment through Conventional lecture method and NHT strategy from both groups from GGHS Nagri Tutial in Tehsil Lora of District Abbottabad.

DATA ANALYSIS

The hypotheses were tested by using independent sample t-test and paired sample t-test hypothesis-wise. The data were evaluated by calculating mean and standard deviation. An independent t-test was used to analyze the significance of the difference between the experimental group and control group. The significance of the difference between the mean scores of the control group and experimental group was taken on the value of 0.05. The test was applied hypothesis-wise.

Pre-Test Analysis on Application Level of Achievement

Comparison of control and experimental groups on pre-test scores for application level on student's achievement in chemistry at secondary level is given in the table 1.

Table 1

Comparison of Pre-Test of Application Level on Students Achievement

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Control	30	3.20	1.88	58	0.80	4.22
Experimental	30	2.83	1.62			

P<0.05

The data analysis revealed that the experimental group had a lower pre-test mean score (2.83) than the control group (3.20), with a minor difference of 0.37. Table 1 indicates that both groups had similar application-level achievement scores before the intervention. The t-value (0.80) at df (58) and p-value (4.22) exceeded the significance level ($p < 0.05$), indicating no statistically significant difference. Thus, both groups were equivalent in their pre-test chemistry achievement at the application level. Further analysis was shown in graph.

Figure 2: Comparison of Experimental and Control Group Pre-Test for Application Level

Result showed in table were more evident with the help of the column graph. Graph showed that both control and experimental group had same mean score for application before the experiment.

Post-Test Analysis on Application Level of Achievement

The analysis for post-test scores of application level for student’s achievement is given below.

Table 2

Comparison of Post-Test of Application Level on Students Achievement

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Control	30	17.76	3.67	58	6.6	0
Experimental	30	22.86	2.1			

P<0.05

The analysis of post-test scores (Table 2) showed that the experimental group outperformed the control group in application-level achievement in chemistry, with mean scores of 22.86 and 17.76, respectively. The t-value (6.60) at df (58) and p-value (0.00) indicated a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). This confirms that the experimental group showed greater improvement, highlighting the effectiveness of the intervention. It can be concluded that there was a significant difference in post-test application-level achievement between the experimental and control groups in chemistry. This indicates that the students were not at the same level after the intervention. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}), stating that the NHT strategy has no effect on students' application-level achievement in chemistry, was rejected.

Figure 3: Comparison of Experimental and Control Group for Post-Test of Application Level

Result showed in table were more evident with the help of the column graph. Graph showed that both control and experimental group had different mean score for application after the experiment. Graph showed that Experimental group post-test mean score is higher than control group.

Retention-Test Analysis for Application Level

Analysis of application level of control and experimental group was done with the help of independent sample t-test and table and graph was plotted. The detailed analysis of retention test was given in table 3.

Table 3

Comparison of Retention -Test of Application Level on Students Achievement

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
Control	30	10.36	3.48	58	16.46	0
Experimental	30	22.36	1.93			

$P < 0.05$

The retention test results revealed that the experimental group had a higher mean score (22.36) compared to the control group (10.36) for application-level achievement in chemistry. Table 3 shows a significant difference between the groups, with a t-value of 16.46 at df (58) and a p-value of 0.00, which is below the 0.05 significance level. This indicates a notable improvement in retention for the experimental group. Therefore, it is concluded that the groups differed significantly in retention scores. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_{02}), stating that the NHT strategy has no effect on retention at the application level in chemistry, was rejected. Result showed in table were more evident with the help of the column graph.

Figure 5: Comparison of Experimental and Control Group for Retention -Test of Application Level

Graph showed that both control and experimental group had different mean score for retention of application level. Graph showed that Experimental group retention test mean score is higher than control group.

FINDINGS

The study's results are arranged in this chapter according to the objectives and hypotheses of the study. The data was evaluated using independent sample and paired sample techniques, and the outcomes are described below.

- The score of the experimental group taught through NHT strategy was significantly higher than the group taught through traditional lecture method. The NHT cooperative learning strategy significantly enhances students' achievement in chemistry, as indicated by a highly significant statistical difference (Table 1).
- The score of NHT strategy group was significantly higher for application level of achievement than the group taught through traditional lecture method. The NHT strategy improves students' application level of achievement in chemistry, demonstrating its effectiveness in fostering cognitive skills (Table 2).
- The score of experimental taught through NHT strategy was significantly higher for retention than the group taught through traditional lecture method. Students taught through the NHT strategy exhibit improved retention of chemistry concepts, suggesting its effectiveness in long-term learning (Table 3).

- The experimental group outperform control group on application level of retention also. The strategy enhances retention at the application level, further strengthening students' ability to apply knowledge effectively (Table 4).

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that the *Numbered Heads Together* (NHT) strategy significantly enhances students' application-level achievement in chemistry. Students who were taught through NHT outperformed their peers who received traditional lecture-based instruction, particularly in tasks requiring them to apply concepts in new situations. This improvement can be attributed to the collaborative nature of NHT, which requires every group member to engage, think critically, and explain content in their own words. This aligns with previous research showing the effectiveness of NHT in improving application-level achievement across subjects (Aditya, Jannah, & Nurhas, 2022; Surati et al., 2021; Wangmo, 2019). Through this cooperative learning structure, learners become active participants, which fosters deeper understanding and encourages them to apply theoretical knowledge to real-life problem-solving in chemistry. Additionally, the study found that NHT positively influenced students' retention of chemistry content. The structured interaction and repeated retrieval of concepts during group discussions contributed to long-term memory formation. These findings support the idea that strategies involving peer explanation and collaborative problem-solving can significantly boost retention (Sibomana, Karegeya, & Sentongo, 2021; Kusumawati, 2022). Students exposed to NHT were more likely to retain applied knowledge over time, suggesting that the active learning model embedded in NHT facilitates not only immediate academic success but also enduring comprehension. This highlights the value of using NHT regularly in chemistry classrooms to build both conceptual application and lasting retention.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study confirm that the Numbered Heads Together (NHT) strategy significantly improves female students' achievements and retention in secondary-level chemistry. The results indicate that students taught using NHT demonstrated higher overall achievement and retention particularly at the application level, compared to those taught through traditional lecture methods. The rejection of the null hypotheses (H_{01} – H_{04}) validates the effectiveness of NHT in enhancing learning outcomes. To ensure the proper application of the NHT strategy, several conditions were met: students were grouped heterogeneously to foster peer learning, clear instructions were provided to ensure active participation, and the teaching sessions were structured to allow collaborative discussion, individual accountability, and equal opportunities for all students to contribute. Additionally, the teaching time was kept consistent across experimental and control groups to eliminate external influences. These conditions facilitated an engaging, student-centered learning environment, making NHT a viable and effective instructional approach for improving conceptual understanding and long-term retention in chemistry education.

Recommendations

- NHT strategy may be used for improving female student's achievements and retention for chemistry teachings.
- NHT strategy may be used for improving achievements and retention for the learning of application level. Therefore, it is recommended for teachers may be trained to develop NHT strategy based lesson for the learning of application level.
- It is recommended for future researchers to investigate teacher attitudes, challenges, and barriers in adopting NHT to provide insights for improving its implementation.
- It is recommended for future researchers to conduct studies focusing on how NHT benefits students with diverse learning needs, including students with learning disabilities and gifted students.

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